

Mini-Workshop on Preparing for PRACE Exascale systems

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Abstract

PRACE-5IP WP7 T7.2 organised a mini-workshop on Preparing for PRACE Exascale Systems on June 1, 2017 at the Forschungszentrum Jülich (FZJ), Germany. This paper discusses the objectives, talks, and outcomes of the workshop.

1. Introduction

PRACE has been supporting to European HPC researchers towards Exascale for several years especially with works produced by Task 7.2 of WP7. In this direction, several technical works have been carried out on the evaluation of the potential of state-of-the-art tools/techniques and scientific applications for future European extreme-scale systems [1]. The current PRACE-5IP task has an increased focus on PRACE application enablement on the road to Exascale, and aims to have a major impact in targeting the challenges of future European HPC systems due to its experience in the earlier implementations.

PRACE-3IP Task 7.2 of WP7 “HPC Tools and Techniques” (June 2012 - May 2014) focused on the analysis of the state-of-the-art HPC tools and techniques, as well as the issues when applying those to European multi-petaflop systems. For this purpose, an extensive survey on the available HPC tools and techniques was carried out by the partners in connection with some of the European Exascale projects and a detailed report was presented in [2]. Eighteen PRACE Whitepapers were produced to analyse how those could be applied to applications within WP7 and to other scientific codes with a forward-looking view for enabling and scaling for Exascale [3].

PRACE-4IP Task 7.2A of WP7 “Evaluation of Tools and Techniques for Future Exascale Systems” (February 2015 - April 2017) focused on developing links with the emerging CoEs (Centres of Excellence) to understand their HPC requirements and investigating the various programming tools, languages, libraries and algorithms needed for future Exascale systems. T7.2A designed questionnaires to get more understanding of the requirements of the CoEs, and the analysis of the questionnaire responses was documented in [4]. As a result of this analysis, fifteen technical works were produced, some of which were increasingly aligned with FET-HPC (Future and Emerging Technologies) projects to better share the knowledge and expertise [5].

PRACE-5IP Task 7.2 of WP7 "Preparing for PRACE Exascale Systems" started at the PRACE-5IP Kick-Off meeting in Athens, Greece on February 1, 2017 [6]. T7.2-5IP specifically focuses on emerging European extreme-scale systems, investigating new tools and techniques by applying them to important applications. The

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task is divided into two phases: A survey phase that will be guided by ongoing technical engagement with the applications of CoEs and with European Exascale projects, mainly FET-HPC (January 2017 - January 2018) and an exploitation phase that will include performing a number of mini-projects using well-known application codes and next generation technologies (January 2018 - April 2019). Building on the initial contacts set up in PRACE-3IP and PRACE-4IP, T7.2-5IP organised a mini-workshop within the PRACE-5IP WP7 Face2Face meeting that was held at Forschungszentrum Jülich (FZJ), Germany on June 1, 2017 [7][8]. The objective of the workshop was to bring together representatives from the CoEs, FET-HPC projects and PRACE applications experts. Inspired by the workshop, PRACE T7.2 partners will propose mini-project topics for the exploitation phase of the task as decided in the planning of the task at the PRACE-5IP Kick-Off meeting.

The layout of this paper is as follows: Section 2 explains the objectives of the Exascale workshop, and introduces its participants. Section 3 presents the schedule, talks and a qualitative classification of the talks. Section 4 discusses the outcomes of the workshop.

2. Objectives and Participants

In line with the objectives of T7.2-5IP, the aim of the workshop was to provide WP7 and the wider community with a clearer view of both the Exascale requirements being set by the CoEs, as well as the tools and techniques emerging from FET-HPC projects. The central aim of the workshop was for PRACE experts within T7.2-5IP to better familiarize themselves with the technologies coming out of the European Exascale projects (especially FET-HPC projects), and to continue to familiarise themselves with CoE requirements. The objective was to support collaborations that test emerging tools, techniques, and prototypes of the FET-HPC projects using applications of relevance to the CoEs during the exploitation phase of the task.

CoEs represent the European Application expertise [9], and were encouraged to present their use cases and challenges. FET-HPC projects develop the next generation prototype European Exascale tools [10], and were encouraged to present solutions that address the needs of CoEs on the path towards Exascale. The workshop acted as a venue for match-making between the PRACE WP7, CoEs and FET-HPC projects, where the PRACE experts would then subsequently work closely with the FET-HPC team to exploit their technology on CoE-relevant applications using European extreme-scale systems.

All CoEs and FET-HPC projects were invited to give a talk at the workshop via emails to the general mailing lists *coe-projects@prace-ri.eu* and *fethpc-projects@prace-ri.eu*, as well as via contacts given in each of their web sites and Point of Contact (PoC) for each CoE [4]. Seven out of nine CoEs and twelve out of nineteen FET-HPC projects were represented at the workshop.

The following CoEs were represented at the workshop:

- E-CAM, An e-infrastructure for software, training and consultancy in simulation and modelling (<https://www.e-cam2020.eu>)
- ESIWACE, Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe (<https://www.esiwace.eu>)
- MaX, Materials design at the eXascale (<http://www.max-centre.eu>)
- POP, Performance Optimisation and Productivity (<https://pop-coe.eu>)
- CoeGSS, Center of Excellence for Global Systems Science (<http://coegss.eu>)
- EoCoE, Energy oriented Centre of Excellence for computer applications (<http://www.eocoe.eu>)
- BioEXCEL, Centre of Excellence for Biomolecular Research (<http://bioexcel.eu>)

The following FET-HPC projects were represented at the workshop:

- MANGO, Exploring Manycore Architectures for Next-Generation HPC systems (<http://www.mango-project.eu>)
- MontBlanc, European approach towards scalable and power efficient HPC platform (<http://montblanc-project.eu>)
- NextGenIO, Next Generation I/O for Exascale (<http://www.nextgenio.eu>)
- SAGE, Percipient StorAGe for Exascale Data Centric Computing (<http://www.sagestorage.eu>)
- ExaNoDe, European Exascale Processor Memory Node Design (<http://exanode.eu>)
- ExaHyPe, An Exascale Hyperbolic PDE Engine (<http://exahype.eu>)

- ESCAPE, Energy-efficient Scalable Algorithms for Weather Prediction at Exascale (<http://www.hpc-escape.eu>)
- ExCAPE, Exascale Compound Activity Prediction Engine (<http://excape-h2020.eu>)
- ANTAREX, AutoTuning and Adaptivity appRoach for Energy efficient eXascale HPC systems (<http://www.antarex-project.eu>)
- ALLScale, An Exascale Programming, Multi-objective Optimisation and Resilience Management Environment Based on Nested Recursive Parallelism (<http://www.allscale.eu/home>)
- READEX, Runtime Exploitation of Application Dynamism for Energy-efficient eXascale computing (<http://www.readex.eu>)
- INTERTWinE, Programming Model INTERoperability ToWards Exascale (<http://www.intertwine-project.eu>)

PERMON (Parallel, Efficient, Robust, Modular, Object-oriented, Numerical) toolbox was also presented at the workshop as a solution for extreme scale applications. (<http://permon.it4i.cz>)

3. Talks

The mini-workshop was organised within the PRACE-5IP WP7 Face2Face meeting and was held in two of its sessions. The schedule of the workshop is listed below.

Session A

11:00 - 11:10 Welcome

(CoE Presentations)

11:10 - 11:15 E-CAM, Alan O’Cais (Juelich) and Godehard Sutmann (Juelich)

11:15 - 11:20 ESiWACE, Joachim Biercamp (DKRZ)

11:20 - 11:25 MaX, Daniel Wortmann (Juelich)

11:25 - 11:30 POP, Jesus Labarta (BSC)

11:30 - 11:35 CoeGSS, Bastian Koller (HLRS)

11:35 - 11:40 EoCoE, Paul Gibbon (Juelich)

11:40 - 11:45 BioEXCEL, Rossen Apostolov (KTH)

(FET-HPC Presentations)

11:45 - 11:50 MANGO, Jose Flich (UPV)

11:50 - 11:55 MontBlanc-3, Jesus Labarta (BSC)

11:55 - 12:00 NextGenIO, Nick Brown(EPCC) and George Beckett (ED)

12:00 - 12:05 SAGE, Dirk Pleiter (Juelich)

12:05 - 12:10 ExaNoDe, Dirk Pleiter (Juelich)

12:10 - 12:15 ExaHyPe, Sven Koepfel (FIAS)

12:15 - 12:20 ESCAPE, Alastair Mckinstry (ICHEC)

12:20 - 12:25 ExCAPE, Vladimir Chupakhin (J&J)

12:25 - 12:30 PERMON and ANTAREX, David Horak (VŠB-TUO)

Session B

13:30 - 13:35 ALLScale, Thomas Heller (Fau)

13:35 - 13:40 READEX, Venkatesh Kannan (ICHEC)

13:40 - 13:45 INTERTWInE, Nick Brown(EPCC) and George Beckett (ED)

13:45 - 15:00 Questions, Discussion and Closure

A summary of the talks is provided in Table 1 and Table 2 in terms of main CoE-applications (developed or used within the CoE), the specific needs of the CoE-applications with respect to Exascale, novel prototype tools/techniques developed by FET-HPC projects and what challenges FET-HPCs target to address towards future extreme scale systems.

As a consequence of the move towards European extreme scale systems, there is an increasing demand for new and improved scalable numerical algorithms and tools that address existing and upcoming complexities associated with the overhead of data movement, distribution of data/tasks, I/O and storage requirements and fault tolerance. In terms of future-looking approaches on the road to Exascale, there has been an increasing interest in building a reliable HPC platform based on many core architectures, which will comprise I/O architectures and storage architectures that support ever increasing performance requirements. This is supported with the design of

state-of-the-art prototypes that provide efficient, flexible, portable, resilient, scalable, interoperable and energy efficient parallel programming on tomorrow's Exascale supercomputers.

CoE	Domain	Applications	Requirements
E-CAM	Materials Science	Open Path Sampling; IMD; Wannier90; Onetep; Siesta; PaPIM; DL_Meso; MP2C; Ludwig; Espresso++	Error control of coupling between different refinements levels, Load balancing and Task scheduling on heterogeneous systems; Fault tolerance and resilience
ESiWACE	Earth System Modelling	EC-Earth; ICON	Efficiency and scalability, High memory bandwidth; Very high I/O and storage demands, Stable HPC environment
MaX	Materials Design	Quantum Espresso; Siesta; Fleur; Yambo; Aiida	Scalability, Load balancing, High-throughput, Double precision real/complex arithmetic; Linear Algebra Libraries
POP	Performance Optimisation	Extrae; Paraver; Score-P; Scalasca; TAU; Vampir; Cube; Dimemas; Extra-P	Testing environment
CoeGSS	Global systems Science	GSS Workflow	High-speed, high-bandwidth network; In-situ (live) data management/data analytics
EoCoE	Energy	MDFT, PV-NEGF; Nowcast, CP2K; SHEMAT; Metawalls; ParFlow+p4est; ESIAS; ALYA; Gysela	Modeling complex geometries, Applying very high-spatial resolution physically-based models; Enhanced sampling techniques; Scalability
BioEXCEL	Biomolecular Modelling	GROMACS; QM/MM/CPMD; Docking/HADDOCK	Low-latency networks, High-bandwidth and Large memory; Resiliency/fault tolerance, Dynamic (task) scheduling; Multi-scale algorithms; Task Parallelism

Table 1 A summary of the CoE presentations at the Exascale workshop

3.1. Qualitative Classification of Talks

The challenges of Exascale computation require efforts at each level of granularity in an HPC research ecosystem. As a qualitative measure of which aspects were emphasized in the Exascale workshop presentations, one can categorize the issues they address at *node (N)*, *system (S)* and *infrastructural (I)* levels, and according to their emphasis on *tools (T)*, *methods (M)*, *hardware architecture (HA)*, or *software architecture (SA)*. While these categories are clearly inadequate to summarize the full scope of any CoE or FET-HPC project, they serve to highlight commonalities between the areas of interest presented at the workshop.

The node, system and infrastructural scales refer to challenges that relate to the technology of individual computational units, clusters of units, and operations across a range of such clusters, respectively. The tools category refers to software packages, libraries, and other devices that provide a general solution to a specific class of problems. The methods category refers to algorithms, programming models, and other methodological developments in computation. The hardware architecture category refers to design and evaluation of specific processing, interconnection and storage technologies. The software architecture category refers to software designs that support workflows, interoperability, and other concerns beyond specific algorithms and methodology. Within this classification, Table 3 presents an overview of the summaries in Table 1 and Table 2.

FET-HPC	Area	Prototypes	Contributions
MANGO	Manycore Architectures	LLVM backend for Vector/GPU-like cores; Global RT Management System based on SLURM	Infrastructure for interconnecting FPGAs; Energy-efficient cooling
MontBlanc	HPC Platform	ARM-based MontBlanc prototype and mini-clusters	Compute node design based on ARM architecture; A software ecosystem and multiscale simulation methodology
NextGenIO	Parallel I/O	Prototype based on Non-volatile RAM with 3D XPoint technology; Scheduler; IOWS	Hardware platform prototype; Software to enable application execution; Understanding the applications I/O profiles and typical I/O workloads
SAGE	Storage	Unified Object Based Storage Infrastructure	Build a data centric computing platform; Create hierarchical storage architecture
ExaNoDe	Node Level Design	Integrated prototype based on Multi-Chip-Module	Enablement of new complex designs; Improved compute density; Improved data transport capabilities
ExaHyPe	Software - PDE	Hyperbolic PDE Engine	Communication-avoiding high order schemes; Tree-Structured Cartesian meshes; Code generation for single core performance
ESCAPE	Software - Weather Prediction	Weather prediction algorithms; Energy performance simulators	Create a flexible and sustainable weather and climate prediction system; Mapping to novel hardware
ExCAPE	Software - Prediction	Compound Activity Prediction Engine	Handling highly imbalanced, very large and diverse data; Conformal prediction using Machine Learning
PERMON [†]	Software - Numerical Library	PERMON Toolbox	Build machine learning programs for better performance; Potential mappings to existing multi-node HPC libraries
ANTAREX	Software - Energy Efficiency	libVersioningCompiler; mARGOT; Clava; Examon; Power Manager	Express the application self-adaptivity; Runtime manage and auto-tune applications for green and heterogeneous HPC
ALLScale	Software - Scalability Portability, Resilience	AllScale API	Unified Parallel Programming Model; Explore recursive task parallelism; Auto-tuning; Code-versioning; Fault tolerance; On-line monitoring
READEX	Software - Energy Efficiency	READEX tool suite	Identification and analysis of dynamism in HPC applications; Tuning hardware-, -, system- and application-level parameters for optimising performance and energy efficiency
INTERTWInE	Software - Interoperability	GASPI + MPI; MPI + tasks; Resource Manager API	Interoperability between APIs, To advance necessitates changes and improvements to both API specification and implementation

Table 2 A summary of the FET-HPC presentations at the Exascale workshop

[†] PERMON is a library developed at the IT4I for extreme scale applications.

CoE	Node	System	Infrastructure
E-CAM		SA, M	
ESiWACE		M, HA	HA
MaX	HA, M	SA, M	
POP			HA
CoeGSS		HA	SA, T
EoCoE		SA, M	
BioEXCEL	HA, M	HA, M	
FET-HPC	Node	System	Infrastructure
MANGO		HA	
MontBlanc	HA	SA, HA, M	
NextGenIO		HA, M	
SAGE		HA, SA	
ExaNoDe	HA	HA	
ExaHyPe	M	M	
ESCAPE	HA	HA, SA	SA
ExCAPE		M	M
PERMON	M	M	
ANTAREX	M	M	
ALLScale		T, M	
READEX	T, M	T, M	
INTERTWInE	T, M	T, M	

Table 3 Qualitative classifications of summaries from Table 1 and Table 2 with respect to scale and category

Table 4 tallies the contents of Table 3 by scale and category, to show which areas were addressed by several presentations.

	Node	System	Infrastructure
Tools	2 FET-HPC	3 FET-HPC	1 CoE
Methods	2 CoE, 3 FET-HPC	5 CoE, 9 FET-HPC	1 FET-HPC
Hardware arch.	2 CoE, 3 FET-HPC	3 CoE, 6 FET-HPC	2 CoE
Software arch.		3 CoE, 3 FET-HPC	1 CoE, 1 FET-HPC

Table 4 Count of the presentations sorted by scale, category and type of the project

The information in Table 4 highlights three important experiences from the workshop:

- There is a clear emphasis on methods and hardware architecture at the node and system scales, where many CoE and FET-HPC project interests align.
- The CoE presentations placed relatively little emphasis on specific tools, this category was primarily addressed by FET-HPC projects at the node and system scales.
- There is little overlap at the scale of infrastructural challenges. This can be attributed to the workshop's scope of matching exploratory prototype technology with scientific challenges, as technology prototypes at infrastructure scale can be prohibitively expensive, and the related challenges demand greater effort than mini-project proposals can encompass. It is still worth noting that a European Exascale effort should include a different arena where problems of this magnitude can be addressed.

4. Outcomes

Building on the work carried out in PRACE-3IP T7.2 and PRACE-4IP T7.2A, the PRACE-5IP T7.2 Exascale workshop was organised in the context of preparing European researchers for future extreme scale systems as we continue to face the challenges of Exascale computing. This workshop concentrated on the current Exascale requirements of CoEs, knowledge around Exascale focused tools and techniques emerging from FET-HPC projects, and how PRACE can best direct its expertise to help prepare and enable applications that are of direct relevance to the CoEs, by investigating new and novel state-of-the-art prototype tools developed by the FET-HPCs.

The Exascale workshop provided a great engagement of T7.2-5IP partners with the CoE and FET-HPC representatives. As an outcome of the workshop, PRACE-5IP WP7 T7.2 partners will submit mini-project topics relevant to CoEs and FET-HPC projects that will be carried out during the exploitation phase of the task, and will be written up as White Papers. All of the tools and techniques to be investigated during the exploitation phase should be of interest to the vast majority of the CoEs and the European HPC community more widely. For this reason, collaboration between PRACE, CoEs and the FET-HPC projects (as well as other Exascale research and development projects) is highly recommended for the exploitation work.

4.1. Mini-projects for the Exploitation Phase of T7.2

Several new project ideas and collaboration opportunities were discussed at the workshop, and T7.2-5IP partners contacted representatives with whom they will collaborate after the workshop. Some partners contacted FET-HPC projects which were not present at the workshop, but have shared interests with the participants. Moreover, some of the CoE/FET-HPC representatives proposed mini-project topics and expressed their interest in collaborating with a PRACE partner.

Currently, five separate main topics have been identified as being important to enable European applications on the road to Exascale. These topics are: Programming Model Design, Scalable Libraries and Algorithms, Energy Efficiency, Debuggers and Profilers and I/O Management. Application domains vary from CFD, neuroscience, computational mechanics, weather forecasting and bimolecular modelling to molecular dynamics. Key elements to be focused on are optimisation, performance, scalability, energy efficiency, task scheduling, communication overhead and fault tolerance. Although the contacts have been initiated between the T7.2-5IP partners and their collaborators from CoEs/FET-HPC projects, the planning of the mini-projects is still on going. According to the planned timeline, approximately ten mini-projects will be proposed in the final quarter of 2017.

References

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